

PHASE SEPARATION BEHAVIOR OF RUBBER-MODIFIED EPOXIES DURING CURING

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ABSTRACT

Addition of carboxyl-terminated butadiene acrylonitrile copolymer (CTBN) to uncured epoxy formulations can greatly improve the crack resistance of cured epoxy materials. Phase separation during curing is an essential prerequisite for the toughness enhancement of modified epoxies. In this investigation, a tracing monitoring study was conducted by means of the combination of laser transmission and optical microscopy to investigate the occurrence and development of phase separation during curing of a CTBN-modified trifunctional epoxy resin, aiming at uncovering the laws and characteristics of the phase separation behavior of the system. In addition, the results of morphological examination for the cured modified epoxy were also presented.

INTRODUCTION

The potential use of graphite fiber resin matrix composites to achieve weight savings in aircraft and space applications is well documented. High toughness is one of the important design requirements for fiber reinforced resin matrix composites. The use of liquid carboxyl-terminated butadiene acrylonitrile copolymer (CTBN) to improve the toughness of epoxy resin composites has been reported in a number of investigations (1-4). Addition of CTBN to epoxy can greatly improve the crack resistance of cured epoxy materials. A cured rubber-modified material usually exhibits a two phase structure of finely dispersed rubber rich domains bonded to the epoxy matrix. The phase separation during curing is an essential prerequisite for the toughness enhancement of modified epoxies. Therefore, understanding of phase separation behavior during curing may lead to better design and manufacture of toughened materials (1,5).

In this investigation, an effective tracing monitoring study was conducted by means of the combination of laser transmission and optical microscopy to investigate the occurrence and development of phase separation during curing of a CTBN-modified trifunctional epoxy resin, aiming at uncovering the laws and characteristics of the phase separation behavior of the system. In addition, the results of a complementary morphological examination by means of optical and scanning electron microscopy for the cured modified epoxy were also presented.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: The trifunctional epoxy used was 4,5-epoxycyclohexane -1,2-dicarboxylate diglycidyl (TDE-85 epoxy resin) with epoxy equivalent weight of 117g. The modifier used was a CTBN rubber, with $M_n=2807$, equivalent carboxyl=0.0558phrg. and acrylonitrile content=26.11%. Diamino diphenyl sulfone (DDS) was the curing agent, BF_3 . MEA was added as a catalyst.

The epoxy and CTBN of equal weight were prereacted to no more than 1% of the initial equivalent carboxyl group per hundred grams. The modified system contained 10 phr CTBN.

Turbidity study: In situ phase separation was monitored by changes of laser intensity transmitted through a sample consisting of a degassed epoxy formulation in a glass tube sandwiched between two heated metal blocks in a temperature control sector (Fig.1). The light beam was a He-Ne laser ($\lambda=632.8\text{nm}$). The intensity of light transmitted through the sample was monitored by a photodiode connected to a detector and recorder. The apparatus was covered by black cloth in order to minimize stray light from the background.

Morphological study: Thin layers of neat and modified epoxy formulations with definite thickness sandwiched between two precleaned glass slides were prepared by mechanically dip coating and pressing and cured under different conditions. Morphological examinations of the thin layer sample and fracture surfaces of cured epoxies were made with optical and scanning electron microscopy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Representative isothermal light intensity-cure time curve is shown in Fig.2. The laser transmission results showed that the light transmitted through the sample was constant throughout cure of the neat epoxy system. However, the initial mixture of the rubber-modified system was optically clear within the cure temperature range, therefore, the prereacted rubber was considered to be compatible with the neat epoxy system at the beginning of cure. During curing, various changes in the system lowered the compatibility of the components, and the mixture turned from optically clear to cloudy. The laser transmission results showed that the light transmitted through the sample decreased with the development of phase separation. The first indication of light intensity transmitted through the sample signaled the onset of phase separation. The end of phase separation was indicated by the levelling off of the curve.

The light transmission results are included in Fig.3, with the gelation line and a line representing 95% decrease of the initial light intensity included to provide an estimate of how rapidly the phase separation of the modified epoxies developed. Most of the phase separation occurred well before gelation, although some changes were observed afterwards, as has been reported (6,7).

Optical microscopy has the advantage of looking at the sample at any moment during curing without quenching or fracture but has the disadvantage of a relative lower magnification and the fact that the light forms a projected picture of all the layers through the thickness of the sample. Representative optical micrographs of the modified systems isothermally cured for different time and cured at different temperatures are shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5.

Neat epoxy systems without rubber are transparent and do not show phase separation. Phase separation is evident from all optical micrographs of samples modified with CTBN and quenched by gelation. No obvious morphological change for the modified system was observed after gelation. Contrasting above results with laser transmission results, it may be concluded that the minor morphological change after gelation is only local morphological structure perfection or the separation out of smaller dispersed particles in the larger ones.

In our trifunctional system, the rubbery domains are in the shape of shell and core. Although the outer boundaries in the shells are linked to the

epoxy matrix, the inside core is totally incompatible. The shell has an average diameter of 50-200 μ m, and the core diameter is 10-30 μ m. There was one or several cores in a shell. The shell and core shape may be formed since the epoxy is attached to the prereacted rubber and therefore surrounds the rubber droplets. This morphology has also been found in SEM of the fractured surfaces of the cured specimens (Fig.6). In the optical microscopy case, the morphology is that of the cured system without any fracture and also exhibits the shape of shell and core. This indicated that the morphology of a modified system is determined by cure condition (i.e., curing temperature and time) rather than by a later stage such as mechanical fracture. Fig.4 exhibits the morphology development of the modified system cured at 135 $^{\circ}$ C for different time. Fig. 4(a) 9 min., (b) 17min, (c)27min. and the gel time of the system at 135 $^{\circ}$ C is 19 minutes. The micrographs indicated that most of the phase separation occurred before gelation, the morphology had no obvious changes after gelation. The shell and core structure was formed step by step, the shell was formed at first well before gelation and the core appeared at a later stage.

The mean size of the dispersed shell and core structure decreased with increase in cure temperature (Fig.5). When the curing temperature was too high, an imperfect phase separation and indistinct phase boundaries resulted from instant gelation (Fig.5c).

Optical and SEM micrographs of the cured specimens of CTBN modified TDE-85 epoxy showed obvious two phase structure and excellent interfacial bonding between matrix and dispersed particles. Meanwhile, there were many sub-inclusions in the dispersed rubbery particles (Fig.6,7). The volume fraction of the dispersed phase particles calculated with Spektor chord analysis method (8) showed an excess volume (Table 1).

Table 1. Volume fraction of dispersed phase vs. cure temperature

T($^{\circ}$ C), (a)	70	110	130	150
v ^(b)	0.188	0.146	0.123	0.089

(a) Cure temperature.

(b) Volume fraction of dispersed phase determined by Spektor chord method.

This indicates that some of the epoxy may have been included in the rubbery phase. The multiphase structure inside the dispersed particles (Salam structure) is regarded as an essential structure factor to obtain optimum toughness.

CONCLUSIONS

The combination of laser transmission and optical microscopy is a convenient and effective technique to study phase separation behavior during curing for rubber-modified epoxy system. The tracing observation results showed that most of the phase separation occurred well before gelation, while some relatively localized compositional changes within the sample continued to take place beyond the gel point. The rubbery domains were in the shape of shell and core, and the shell was formed prior to the core.

CTBN-modified TDE-85 epoxy system has an obvious two phase structure, and excellent interfacial bonding between matrix and dispersed particles, which is essential for epoxy toughening. The dispersed particles exhibit multiphase structure themselves, with many subinclusions inside.

Fig.1 Schematic diagram of the laser transmission apparatus

Fig.2 Isothermal light transmission curve of modified epoxy
 t_{co} , 95% decrease of the initial light intensity.
 t_{cc} , End of phase separation.

Fig.3 Phase separation characteristics of the modified epoxy

Fig.4a Optical micrograph of modified epoxy cured at 135°C for 9 minutes.

Fig.4b Optical micrograph of modified epoxy cured at 135°C for 17 minutes.

Fig.4c Optical micrograph of modified epoxy cured at 135°C for 27 minutes.

Fig.5a Optical micrograph of modified epoxy cured at 90°C.

Fig.5b Optical micrograph of modified epoxy cured at 120°C.

Fig.5c Optical micrograph of modified epoxy cured at > 250°C.

Fig.6 SEM of cured modified epoxy.

Fig.7 Optical micrograph of cured modified epoxy.

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